

ISic2923

I.Sicily inscription 2923

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Arancio hypogeum, villa Landolina

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. M(emoria) Anto
2. ni figuli e[t] Leonti[a]e

Apparatus

Text after Manganaro 1993

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175839

EDR 073824

EDCS 13900571

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic2923. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4356970>